

Genre-based Writing Assessment

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Abstract

This essay presents a view towards genre-based writing assessment. The reason for writing this essay is the fact that genre-based writing assessment usually involves thorough textual analysis, which can be a daunting task for those who are unfamiliar with SFL. In this essay, the use of a rubric is recommended. To this end, the essay explains the required knowledge and steps in developing a genre-based writing rubric. While this essay aims to provide fundamental understanding of the genre-based writing assessment, it also implies that SFL knowledge is the most important element for genre-based writing assessment practice.

Keywords: GBA, genre-based, writing rubric, SFL, writing assessment.

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1 Introduction

The Sydney School conceptualizes genre as a staged, goal-oriented social process (Martin & Rose, 2009). In terms of writing, it is a goal-oriented social process because language is used to achieve particular social purposes (e.g., to argue) and to this end, language is used in steps (Hyland, 2004). Moreover, it is said that each genre has its register features, where register is understood as the variation of language determined by the *field*, *tenor* and *mode*¹ (Matthiessen et al., 2010; Schleppegrell, 2001). Based on this idea, a genre has its generic structure and linguistic features, by which the social purpose of the genre is achieved. For an introduction to SFL, I recommend Eggins (2004) and Butt et al. (2012).

The Genre-based Approach (GBA) is an approach to teaching language, which, in this essay, is proposed by the Sydney School or SFL scholars. Among the core tenets of GBA are explicit genre instruction and scaffolding. The former is rooted in SFL, while the latter is in Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development theory (Gibbons, 2015). Derewianka and Jones' (2016) is a useful introduction to GBA. I will focus on the explicit genre instruction, which should be translated into explicit genre assessment for the sake of this essay.

In general, GBA writing assessment involves multilevel SFL-based textual analyses. By referring to the description of the given genre, SFL GBA scholars often break a text down based

¹Field is concerned with the topic or domain of the discourse; Tenor is concerned with the relationships between the interactants; Mode is concerned with the channel of the discourse.

on the generic structure, divide the text into clauses, and analyze the clauses using multiple grammar systems. Emilia's (2005) work is a good example. While this method provides a deep and thick description of the text, analyzing a huge number of texts can be a daunting task. Alternatively, rubrics can be used. Provided that the analyst (a teacher or researcher) is familiar with SFL GBA, a thorough scanning of the text should suffice for the assessment. When carefully developed and communicated, a rubric can be a powerful tool for assessing texts, whether in the classroom or research context (Crusan, 2010; Weigle, 2002).

However, developing a genre-based writing rubric for assessment requires knowledge of (1) how SFL GBA views language (this requires knowledge of the social purpose of the genre), (2) what counts as *constructs* (this requires knowledge of *metalanguage*), and (3) the characteristics of the given genre (its generic structure and linguistic features). Together, these pieces of knowledge ensure the validity and reliability of the rubric as the assessment instrument. For instance, point (1) provides a ground for judging the degree of success of the text; point (2) helps us formulate an operational definition of the constructs; point (3) directs our attention towards the elements to be assessed.

There have been various writing rubrics. The most used rubric might be of Jacob's ESL Composition Profile, which has been leveraged in various academic contexts (Weigle, 2002). However, this kind of rubric covers only general constructs, while genres have their characteristics (Hyland, 2004). Meanwhile, a rubric should be developed based on the task at hand to ensure its validity and reliability (Crusan, 2010). It does not necessarily mean that a rubric is not reusable. Since SFL GBA views genres as text types (Derewianka & Jones, 2016; Emilia, 2005), a genre is assumed to have a stable generic structure and linguistic features. Thus, a rubric for a genre can be used in different contexts. Some genre-based rubrics can be found in Emilia (2011), Hyland (2004), Nagao (2020), and Pessoa et al. (2018).

2 Required Knowledge

This section outlines the knowledge one must possess for developing and using a genre-based writing rubric to assess text.

2.1 SFL GBA view of language or text

Knowing *what language is, what it does, and how it does it* according to SFL GBA may be an important ground for judging the quality of a text². GBA adopts SFL's view of language as a resource for making meaning in context (Derewianka & Jones, 2016; Eggins, 2004). Thus, what language does is "make meaning." This means that SFL GBA emphasizes the semantic aspect of language use, the function of language. Furthermore, the meaning-making process is contextual. This means that SFL GBA also focuses on how vocabulary and grammar are used selectively based on the immediate context (Butt et al., 2012).

In terms of writing assessment, although grammatical accuracy is often an assessed element, primarily in a second or foreign language context, SFL GBA also puts attention on the contextual linguistic choices made in the text. For instance, while a student has used correct grammar, the language may represent spoken language more than written language. In SFL, both are distinguished in terms of the *lexicogrammar*³ complexity. Spoken language is generally grammatically intricate, while written language generally has weightier lexical density (Halliday, 1989). Of course, writing mechanics (e.g., punctuation, spelling, capitalization, etc.) are also under scrutiny since they are conventions. Another example is the use of technical terms, where the writer's ability to build the field of the discourse can be assessed. The level of language

²In SFL, *text* is generally understood as a stretch of meaningful and coherent language of any length (Eggins, 2004).

³Lexicogrammar represents how vocabulary and grammar are used contextually

formality is also examined to judge the writer's understanding of the readers and the overall context in which the text is being exchanged.

Thus, instead of just focusing on the grammatical accuracy, SFL GBA also poses questions like "Is the lexicogrammatical choice appropriate for making and negotiating the meaning in this context?" Furthermore, GBA also emphasizes the function of language to achieve various social purposes. Language or text can be created to argue, to entertain, to describe, to tell stories, to explain, and so forth (Derewianka & Jones, 2016; Emilia, 2011). Knowing that language is used differently in arguing and describing, an analyst or assessor can determine whether the generic structure and lexicogrammatical choices made in the text are appropriate for the given purpose.

2.2 Constructs in writing assessment

The term *construct* refers to what is supposed to be assessed (Weigle, 2002). In general, constructs in writing assessment include grammar, mechanics, organization, arguments, etc. These are too general and implicit. Consequently, we often judge a writing as good, without knowing what exactly it takes to be a good writing (Hyland, 1990). In addition, because it is too general, a few of these constructs cannot be applied in particular genres. For instance, typically, arguments are not assessed in a narrative text, and complication is not an element to be assessed in an argumentative text. The constructs in genre-based writing assessment must be derived from the SFL GBA description of the given genre. SFL makes it easier to formulate and operationalize constructs because it provides explicit terms, known as *metalanguage*.

The term *metalanguage* is understood as language to talk about language (Derewianka & Jones, 2016; Gibbons, 2015). Terms in conventional grammar (e.g., phrase, adjective, passive voice, etc.) can be considered as metalanguage as well. In SFL, it covers a deeper and wider dimension of text. For instance, in assessing an *analytical exposition*⁴ text, terms like *thesis*, *arguments*, and *reiteration* are metalanguage. In terms of arguments, an SFL GBA scholar will use metalanguage such as *attribution*, *modality*, *endorsement*, *graduation* to describe the level of persuasiveness. With the metalanguage, instead of judging "This text is persuasive enough," the analyst will say "The text includes attribution and endorsement to improve the persuasiveness." Or, instead of saying "The text is not cohesive," the analyst can say "The text lacks text connectives."

Metalanguage used in writing assessment is tied to the genre being assessed. One needs to refer to the description of the genre proposed in various SFL GBA literature, or simply learn SFL. The knowledge of genre-specific metalanguage will help them in determining the constructs.

2.3 Generic structure and linguistic features

The generic structure and linguistic features are two overarching constructs in genre-based writing assessment (Emilia, 2011). These two constructs are centered on how the language is staged and used appropriately to achieve the social or communicative purpose (e.g., to mount arguments). In other words, when we assess a text, we first ask, "What is the social purpose of the text?" Then, "Is the text properly staged to achieve its purpose?" Then, "How do the lexicogrammatical choices made realize the function of each stage, which eventually help the text achieve its social purpose?"

2.3.1 Generic structure

SFL GBA scholars claim that we use language in stages to achieve the goal of communication. The presence and structure of the stages construct the generic structure (Gibbons, 2015).

⁴A family of argumentative genres, aiming at arguing of whether something is or is not the case.

Generic structure can be understood as the shared pattern of texts in a given genre. In this case, *stages* are the primary elements that construct the pattern (Schneer, 2014).

An email requesting information, for instance, typically begins with a greeting. Then, perhaps, a brief self-introduction follows, just before the intention is stated. Afterward, the sender may thank the addressee for the cooperation. This pattern can be learned by analyzing a large number of emails with the same purpose, which are known in SFL GBA as *model texts*, looking for choices made by different senders. Stories also have a pattern, though variations may exist. A story typically begins with an orientation to introduce the scene and characters, unless a non-linear plot (e.g., flashback) is applied. We may expect students to know the typical pattern of the text of a genre, and we look for the "similarity" compared to the model texts. However, it does not necessarily mean that we expect students to imitate the model texts, as the model texts only provide choices for the text to achieve its purpose.

Traditionally, an article or essay is divided into at least three parts or stages: introduction, body, and conclusion, regardless of its social purpose. These labels are not descriptive enough; we do not really know what a stage is doing in the text. SFL GBA scholars categorized texts sharing the social purpose and analyzed their shared patterns. Stages are identified and labeled based on their functions. For instance, in an exposition, the introductory stage is labeled *thesis*, because the main function of the stage is to hold the *thesis statement* (Coffin, 2004; Derewianka & Jones, 2016). Furthermore, instead of using *body*, a more functional label is used, *arguments* or *a series of arguments*. Then, instead of using *conclusion*, the last stage is labeled *reiteration* or *reinforcement* because the stage not only concludes but also reiterates or reinforces the thesis statement. In addition, it is important to notice that these functional labels are also metalanguage. Thus, instead of saying "the introduction is clear," one may say "the thesis consists of..." This way, the assessment is more explicit.

In assessing writing, we would look for the presence of all obligatory elements or stages⁵. However, we also look for how those stages are put and related in the text. We may refer to the genre description provided in SFL GBA literature or analyze the model texts and determine the stages and their structures. The labels used, however, must be functional.

2.3.2 Linguistic features

This is the largest construct in the genre-based writing assessment. From this overarching construct, smaller constructs are derived, focusing on the writer's lexicogrammatical choices, by which each stage is functional, and the main social purpose of the text is achieved. Two options are available for assessing this construct. First, we can analyze the linguistic features (the register) at the stage level. Second, we can analyze this construct at the text level. Emilia (2005) provides an example for the former, while Nagao (2020) provides an example for the latter. However, what Emilia did was a full Systemic Functional Grammar (SFG) analysis, while Nagao developed and used a rubric. For this essay, I would suggest using Nagao's approach.

In developing a genre-based writing rubric, we need to know the function of each stage and identify the language used in each stage. Metalanguage provided by SFL is used. For instance, since an analytical exposition argues whether something is or is not the case, expressions like "X is Y" or "X can be Y" may be expected in the thesis and reiteration stages. The metalanguage for this expression is *relational process*, which is vital in an analytical exposition text. A recount text, whose purpose is to tell a story or real event, will exhibit a large proportion of past tense (Emilia, 2011), which is another example.

In an academic writing context, citations are expected because they give a sense of authority. However, not all cited passages are equal. Some cited passages may or may not support the writer's stance. When the cited passages are used to explicitly support the writer's stance or claims, the metalanguage used is *endorsement*; otherwise, it is just an *attribution* (Martin &

⁵Some stages are optional, depending on the genre

White, 2005).

Since each genre has its linguistic features, analyzing model texts will be helpful. Alternatively, an analyst or assessor may refer to SFL GBA literature to identify the linguistic features of the genre.

Originally, SFL assumes that regardless of the genre, language functions to project the experience of reality (what is thought, what happens, what is felt, what is said, etc.), to enact a social relationship (to engage, to persuade, to inform, to ask for information, etc.), and to organize the messages in the text (to build cohesion, to maintain coherence, to ensure logical flow, etc.). These are called *metafunction* (Butt et al., 2012), but I will not go deeper into this. However, it is helpful for the assessor to have a grasp of the concept so that he or she can have a strong theoretical ground for the judgments. Furthermore, learning SFL means learning the metalanguage to use in the rubric, and using metalanguage helps with a more explicit assessment.

Linguistic features as constructs may or may not be shared among genres, because language is used quite differently to achieve different communication goals. With the goals or social purposes in mind, we can judge the appropriateness of the language. However, we also need to consider the *context of situation* or register, consisting of the field, tenor, and mode, which have been mentioned earlier. We know that speaking on the phone and writing an email would exhibit different patterns, though the goal is the same (e.g., to ask for information); this is related to the *mode*. We also know that with the same goal, one may use language rather differently when the interaction partner is a close friend, compared to when the partner is someone with a distant social relationship; this is related to the *tenor*. The point is this: the social purpose may influence the way language is used, but the context determines the appropriateness. This must be an important construct in writing assessment.

The next is this: cohesion and coherence are non-negotiable constructs. This is related to the *textual metafunction*, resonating with the *mode* as a register variable. How the writer organizes the messages, within and between grammatical units, is vital to judge in writing. It is so because recursivity is more tolerated in spoken communication than in written communication. The smooth flow of information is required in written communication because the reader will not have the chance to ask for clarification, and so forth. In terms of fictional writing, however, it works differently, where *complication* does not always follow *orientation*; there is a plot system that manages the flow.

In summary, each genre exhibits its linguistic features, though some genres may share features (e.g., analytical and hortatory expositions). Additionally, linguistic features are more than textual characteristics, but they function to drive the text to its social purpose.

3 Developing a genre-based writing rubric

This section outlines the function and elements of a genre-based writing rubric, as well as steps in developing it. Its values have been explained in many writing assessment literature, such as Crusan (2010) and Weigle (2002). Thus, this section will not provide a comprehensive explanation.

3.1 Function and elements of a genre-based writing rubric

A writing rubric is a tool that provides a means of judging the writer's performance and converts information about it (Klimova, 2011). Scores in the rubric can be converted into useful information regarding the strengths and areas for improvement in the text.

Rubrics are developed as a guide for assessment. They contain "reminders" of what to look for and how to value them. Yet, they are also prone to adaptations. In the classroom, rubrics can be adapted or adopted from a different context. Alternatively, they are developed with

students (Crusan, 2010); the teacher shares with the students the criteria, thresholds, scales, descriptors, and so forth. Revisions may be made in the existing rubrics when the classroom decides to include or remove criteria or adjust the rating scales.

Revisions on rubrics are needed, particularly when the rubrics are based on the writer. For instance, some rubrics may apply to school students and need revisions when they are used to assess university students' writing performance. It is so because older students may be required to perform "better" than younger students. Thus, the criteria and descriptors may need adaptations. This is not the case when the rubrics are based on the genre. The generic structure and linguistic features of a genre apply regardless of the writer. All expositions must have a thesis, a series of arguments, and a reiteration of the thesis. Older students or writers may use more sophisticated vocabulary than younger students. However, considering the tenor, they may be required to use less sophisticated vocabulary when their readers are children. Likewise, school students are required to use, for instance, sophisticated field-specific technical terms when it is an academic text and the target readers are the scientific community.

A genre-based writing rubric, then, captures not only the writer's writing performance, but also the quality of the text in achieving its social purpose. To this end, the rubric needs to have the following elements:

3.1.1 Constructs

Constructs are the ability that we want to assess (Weigle, 2002). In a genre-based writing rubric, the overarching constructs are the generic structure (some call it *schematic structure*) and linguistic features.

Within the schematic structure, the sub-constructs include the presence of the obligatory (and optional) stages, as well as their organization. Within the linguistic features, sub-constructs will depend on the genre being assessed. In general, SFL GBA scholars categorize the linguistic features into field-related, tenor-related, and mode-related features (Derewianka & Jones, 2016). Resonating with this, other scholars use SFL metafunction as the sub-constructs placeholder, such as ideational, interpersonal, and textual metafunctions (Nagao, 2020; Pessoa et al., 2018). Basically, these register or metafunctional categories refer to the language used to build the field (e.g., what the text is about, what happens, etc.), enact social relationships (e.g., to engage with other voices, to persuade the readers, etc.), and organize the text coherently (e.g., to link clauses, sentences, paragraphs, to sign a transition, etc.).

Since genres have their structure and register features, there is no "universal rubric" for all genres. Although the overarching constructs are shared, the sub-constructs are not. For instance, the use of modality (modal verbs and modal adjuncts) may be a construct in argumentative genres, but it is not what to look for in a descriptive text. Similarly, although exposition and discussion texts are members of the argumentative genres family, counterargument (*disclaim*, to use the SFL term) may be required in the latter, but not in the former (Coffin, 2004; Gibbons, 2015).

It is also important to include the features of written language as constructs, at least the writing mechanics. Moreover, in a second and foreign language classroom context, grammatical accuracy should also be assessed, regardless the genre.

3.1.2 Scales or scores

Rubrics can be holistic (a single score based on general impression) or analytic (scores are assigned to each construct) (Weigle, 2002). A genre-based writing rubric must be analytical, though a final score can be derived by adding up all elemental scores.

Scores or scales can be a single number, like in Pessoa et al. (2018) or a range like in Nagao (2020). Some may prefer a single score assigned to a descriptor rather than a range, which is also used in the ESL Composition Profile. It is so because choosing a score from a range may

involve intuitive judgment. However, choosing a score from a range will be useful to explicitly distinguish between two or more students who get, for example, a proficient grade or band.

3.1.3 Descriptors

Descriptors are descriptions of quality tied to a construct and scores (Weigle, 2002). This may be the most challenging element to design because the assessor needs to decide what can describe a score. For instance, what distinguishes between poor and good or good and excellent? The solution to this challenge is the preliminary analysis of the model texts. One may collect texts written in the same genre by beginner, intermediate, and advanced writers. The quality of the generic structure and linguistic features of their texts can be "standards" to formulate the descriptors. In other words, model texts from each category may tell us what to expect from beginner, intermediate, and advanced writers.

For instance, a text written by a beginner writer may be expected to have all obligatory stages. An intermediate writer may be expected to include all obligatory stages plus a few optional stages. Meanwhile, an advanced writer may be expected to have all obligatory and optional stages, without producing any concerns in the text. Pessoa et al. (2018) use 0-4 scores with simple descriptors such as "Poor execution or no use or almost no use of linguistic resources" to "Excellent use of linguistic resources." However, these simple descriptors must be tied to explicit constructs and criteria. For instance, in terms of textual metafunction or mode-related features, one of them is "Linking/signpost words are introduced in the body of the essay." This example was taken from a rubric for assessing an analytical exposition text.

3.2 Steps in developing the rubric

Developing or designing a writing rubric can be a challenging, resource-consuming task. Often, it requires a research project. This subsection only provides general steps to take, which should be further expanded or extended as necessary. Additionally, the following steps assume that an assessor decides to develop a new rubric.

3.2.1 Identifying the social purpose of the text

The assessor identifies the social purpose of the text. In general, SFL GBA has described the social purposes of genres, but the description often focuses on *elemental genres*⁶. Sometimes, one may deal with *macro genres*⁷. Most simply, identifying the social purpose of the text can be done by posing the question, "For what was this text written?" A research article, for instance, is written **to report** the findings of a study. Thus, the text is basically a report. When working with an elemental genre, the social purpose is obvious.

3.2.2 Collecting and analyzing model texts

The assessor collects model texts, taken from various sources (e.g., textbooks, the internet, magazines, etc.) It is important to classify the collected model texts into bands or levels, as mentioned earlier.

Using SFL GBA description of the genre associated with the text, the assessor identifies the generic structure (the potential stages) that build the text. Pay attention to the commonalities across the model texts. Variations may exist, but they should be treated as *choices*.

Using SFG, the assessor analyzes the linguistic features, divided based on register or metafunction. Metalanguage is used in this step to identify constructs in each metafunction. To perform this challenging task, each model text should be divided into clauses, because SFG

⁶Elemental genres: basic genres of text with the social purposes are easy to identify (e.g., narrative, exposition, recount, descriptive, etc.)

⁷Macro genres: complex texts that combine multiple elemental genres (e.g., research article).

analysis typically operates at the clause level (Butt et al., 2012). Following Emilia (2005), the analysis can start from the textual metafunction to identify the topical theme and the overall organization of the text. The presence of other analysts with an SFL background will give great support.

3.2.3 Describing levels

The assessor formulates the levels or bands, along with the scales or scores. Levels can be descriptive (e.g., excellent, good, average, poor) or numerical (e.g., 4, 3, 2, 1). If numerical, one can also use a range (e.g., 86-100, 56-85, 26-55, 0-25). These levels apply to all constructs. I would suggest using both; numerical levels can be statistically calculated or simply added up to derive a final grade.

Each level must be described cautiously. The assessor needs to formulate the discriminating factors (e.g., presence, frequency, appropriateness, etc.), which should be based on the results of model texts analysis. More importantly, the descriptors must contain metalanguage, which is tied to the constructs. For instance, the construct may be *the use of relational process*, and the descriptor for "poor" may be *the text lacks relational process to...*

3.2.4 Designing the rubric

All constructs within each metafunctional category are put together (tabulated) along with the levels and their descriptors. The levels and their descriptors need to be ordered from the lowest to the highest. One may follow the common writing rubrics' structures.

3.2.5 Testing and validating the rubric

The rubric needs to be tested and validated. One may involve SFL GBA experts to review the rubric as well, but the rubric must be tested in a real context. The rubric can be used to assess a number of sample texts (e.g., students' texts). The results of the test should be examined in terms of their reliability. The rubric is reliable if it produces the same results when assessing the same text at different times. Other raters should be involved to overcome biases.

3.2.6 Revising the rubric

Expert validation may result in feedback for revising the rubric. Also, the rubric may fail in the reliability test. If that is the case, the assessor needs to check whether the constructs, levels, or descriptors need to be revised. The rubric needs to be retested after revision. When the rubric is deemed reliable and valid (by tests and experts), it is ready to use.

4 Conclusion

This essay has presented the genre-based writing assessment, which is quite different from other approaches. The difference lies in the constructs, which are influenced by the way SFL GBA views language. While SFL GBA typically performs thorough text analysis based on SFG in writing assessment, this essay suggests using rubrics. Rubrics must be developed based on genres, focusing on their generic structure and linguistic features. Grammatical accuracy and writing mechanics are among the common constructs in writing assessment, which should not be eliminated from the rubrics, particularly in a second or foreign language writing context. The process of developing a genre-based writing rubric involves analyzing model texts and is recursive. The rubric is deemed ready to use when it reaches the rational threshold for reliability and validity.

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